

Associated project to RESILIENCE

Iroooooo14 - Itserr

D4.4 - Prepare DaMSym for Publication to RESILIENCE Marketplace

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Distribution List

Name	Company	Role
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Document Overview

Scope

The global purpose of Work Package 4 (WP4) DaMSym (Data Mining: the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Symbol) is the semantic analysis of key terms found in our case study, namely the text of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed in its various translations. The ITSERR project envisions that advanced knowledge for the history of religious studies will emerge from these studies, but also that new purposely developed cutting-edge IT tools will be made available to fellow scholars for extracting information from the ancient texts under consideration. Language models, particularly those based on Large Language Models (LLM), can be used to analyze the text of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed in order to identify significant semantic patterns. These models will be optimized (e.g., fine-tuning operation) over a wide range of Christian texts for the different translation languages under consideration.

To analyze the text of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed for the purpose of identifying significant semantic patterns, rule-based or probabilistic architecture tools can be used. In particular, Large Language Models (LLMs) may eventually be finetuned to perform a wide range of semantic operations on the Christian texts for the various translation languages under consideration whose amount of data currently available allows it. With these models it will be possible to obtain advanced semantic representations to facilitate the identification of relationships, similarities and deep meanings for key terms in the Creed. Data mining will then be applied to this enriched corpus to extract detailed information about semantic relationships within the Creed, helping us to better understand the theological and historical significance of each term in the various translations and interpretations of the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed.

Objectives

Deliverable 4.4 in its original form had a deadline set for the 1st May 2025 and was written in the following format:

The technical documentation, source code and binaries of DaMSym are packaged as Open Source software for publication to RIs software marketplace such as EOSC/SSHOC, CLARIN, RESILIENCE, etc.

In any case, from the initial draft of this deliverable to the present, the comprehension of the project around DaMSym is progressed and we convened to intervene slightly modifying this description in order to align it to the state of the art in the field of NLP for ancient languages, to make it more detailed and corresponding to the direction we are following in the research and developing process.

This update intervention has been applied also to the other 4 deliverables of WP4 (to date, the first three have been published on Zenodo, the fourth is in publish) that now reflect the nature of our work in a more informative way. Therefore Deliverable 4.4 deadline was rephrased and rescheduled. It thus appears now in this shape:

The technical documentation, source code and binaries of DaMSym tools are packaged as Open Source software for publication to RIs software marketplace such as EOSC/SSHOC, CLARIN, RESILIENCE, etc.

Worded like this, the deliverable 4.4 collects the technical output of WP4. In fact, in Deliverable 4.1.1 “Whitepaper on DaMSym” and in Deliverable 4.1.2 “Whitepaper on the results using DaMSym on Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed” we introduced the development of the tools and the research that highlighted their necessity and feasibility while collecting remarks and suggestions from experts with surveys to update the development path. In Deliverable 4.2 “Training material, manual and documentation for RESILIENCE” we provided the scholarly community with vademecum and user-guide documentation to best exploit the tools and in 4.3 we outlined scientific output discussed in papers and conferences by WP4 members.

This pipeline is concluded with Deliverable 4.4. This document collects the technological output with its technical data sheet and link to the official repositories. Furthermore, this Deliverable explains the tools with Technical data report.

Given the impossibility of aligning the development timeline of the tools with the schedule for the administrative submission and review of the deliverables, a clarification is necessary regarding the completion status of certain outputs.

In particular, as the reviewer Margherita Fantoli observed, the only point that may require further clarification concerns the extent to which a tool indicated as a “Retrieval Tool in the Marketplace” can be considered completed if the “Link to the Operative Web Tool” is not yet available, and whether the “Link to Source Material” is sufficient to fulfil the requirements of WP 4.4.

This inconsistency, rightly pointed out by the deliverable reviewer, has now been addressed by providing in the document the links to the final Training Center and to the final Hortus Marketplace. These links are included directly in the deliverable, even though they do not always coincide with those originally provided in the forms submitted to the reviewer.

The official link to all the resources and tools produced by WP4 that are hosted in the HORTUS website is: <https://damsym-itserr.d4science.org>

This is the official link to the project’s Training Centre, which includes resources related to WP4 as well: <https://training-itserr.d4science.org/>

Structure

We conceive this deliverable as a structured space in which we gather, systematize, and introduce the various scholarly datasets, tools and Large Language Models (LLMs) produced by the activities of the Work Package 4 over the course of the project. This document is intended not only as a repository of outputs but also as a practical guide that allows researchers, developers, and other stakeholders to navigate the resources effectively. The document is organized into sections that reflect both the type of resource (datasets, tools, LLMs) and the language or domain they target. Key sections include the Technical Data Sheets, which provide abstracts, detailed descriptions, and links to shared Excel sheets and PDF summaries. We also provide descriptions of prototyping lab results and deliverables prompted in collaboration with the Fincons Group and evaluations of performance and impact. Supplementary tools, such as converters, lemmatizers, and the Sanskrit tool, are also introduced.

Team

Marianna NAPOLITANO	Unimore	Old Church Slavonic
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Usman NAWAZ	Unipa – Liliana LO PRESTI	Old Church Slavonic
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Maria CASSESE	ISTI-CNR, Pisa	Old Church Slavonic
Igor SPANÒ	Unipa	Sanskrit
Irfan ALÌ	Unipa – Marco LA CASCIA	Sanskrit
Federico IEZZI	Unimore	Latin and Greek
Elia SCAPINI	Unimore	Latin and Greek
Marcella CORNIA	Unimore (WP6)	Latin and Greek
Costanza BIANCHI	Unimore	Coptic
Fabio QUATTRINI	Unimore - Silvia CASCIANELLI	Coptic
Lorenzo BIANCHI	IST-CNR - Fabrizio SEBASTIANI	Coptic
Alejandro MOREO	ISTI-CNR - Fabrizio FALCHI	Coptic

The WP Leader is Fabrizio D’Avenia, while Costanza Bianchi (Research fellow, Fondazione per le scienze religiose, Bologna) and Marianna Napolitano (RTD-A -Unimore) are the Product owners. The team directly involves 4 Phd Candidates: Federico Iezzi (Unimore), Elia Scapini (Unimore), Usman Nawaz (UniPa) and Irfan Alì (UniPa). Ivanza Panzeca (UniPa) and Igor Spanò (UniPa) are the researchers (RTD-A) included in our work package.

As of Oct. 29, the team expanded for the Slavic section with the participation of the Centro Nazionale (ISTI-CNR, Pisa), represented by Maria Cassese, Giovanni Puccetti and Fabrizio Sebastiani. Activities for Latin and Greek languages are fully covered by CNR-ISTI, Pisa, but the preparatory work for this deliverable - specifically, until December 2024 for Greek and until June 2025 for Latin-was covered by WP6. Humanities research for Church Slavonic is supported by WP3 (Criterion). Regarding Coptic, due to the scarcity of data, the work is covered in a partial way and is supervised by a research fellow from the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia.

Technical Data Sheet

With this link, we have introduced a Technical Data Sheet to provide a structured overview of each item produced within WP4, allowing for systematic documentation and easy access. Each entry in the sheet corresponds to a specific resource—be it a dataset, software tool, linguistic model, or retrieval tool—and follows a standardized format that captures essential information for researchers and developers.

For each item, the following characteristics are recorded:

- Language: Specifies the linguistic domain of the item, e.g., Latin, Ancient Greek, Cross-language (Latin and Greek), Church Slavonic, Arabic, or Sanskrit.
- Type of Item: Categorizes the resource, such as a Retrieval Tool, Linguistic Model (e.g., SPhilBERTa), Software (e.g., lemmatizer), Dataset (e.g., corpus), or other types.
- Name: Provides the official name of the item; for retrieval tools, names follow a standard format such as "DaMSym Latin."
- Short Description: Offers a brief explanation of the item's purpose and functionality (not required for retrieval tools).
- Link to Source Material / Repository: Directs users to the code, dataset, or documentation repository for access and reuse.
- Screenshot / Visual Representation: Includes images from the Figma marketplace, screenshots of the tool, or other relevant visuals illustrating the current status of the resource.
- Link to Operative Web Tool: Provides a URL to the live tool, if applicable.
- Future Development Prospects: Highlights planned enhancements, additional features, or potential extensions in the short or long term.
- Additional Information: Contains any other relevant notes, instructions, or context for proper use.

This standardized format ensures that each resource is fully described, easily navigable, and immediately usable by the research community, supporting reproducibility and interoperability across WP4 outputs.

This material is collated in the file attachment Ao8_Technical Data Sheet.

Result of Prototyping Lab and Fincons Deliverables

Overview

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (ITSERR) for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies. (This document is the Proposal for the Analysis Phase of the MarketPlace for Work Package 2, DCS).

Applicable documents (that are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document) include:

- 16/10/2024. VERBALE DI AVVIO ANTICIPATO DELL'ESECUZIONE DEL CONTRATTO PER IL SERVIZIO PER LA CREAZIONE, IL MANTENIMENTO E L'INSTALLAZIONE DI SOFTWARE E SERVIZI ICT DI RICERCA CUSTOMIZZATI – "SOFTWARE LAB", CUP B53C22001770006, CIG B20BDCF4C9, PROT. 167440/2024 DEL 16/10/2024.
- 20/06/2022. D.D. n. 11 del 20/06/2022 - a valere dell'avviso pubblico per il "Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca" finanziato nell'ambito PNRR Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Componente 2, "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" - Linea di investimento 3.1, per la tipologia di intervento il potenziamento di IR presente nel PNIR a priorità alta nell'ambito dell'area ESFRI "Social and Cultural Innovation e contestuale disposizione di impegno di spesa – CIG: B20BDCF4C9".

Reference documents (are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement and Project scope, although they are not repeated in the present document):

- 20/06/2022. D.D. n. 11 del 20/06/2022 - a valere dell'avviso pubblico per il "Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca" finanziato nell'ambito PNRR Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Componente 2, "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" - Linea di investimento 3.1, per la tipologia di intervento il potenziamento di IR presente nel PNIR a priorità alta nell'ambito dell'area ESFRI "Social and Cultural Innovation e contestuale disposizione di impegno di spesa – CIG: B20BDCF4C9".
- 16/12/2024. RS-006-WP2.
- 30/01/2025. Fincons - ITSERR RS-006-WP2 - WP2 - Prototyping Lab Services - Implementation.

Fincons and Work Package 4

In the framework of the aforementioned agreement, WP4 had the opportunity to submit a number of Use Cases that were addressed by Fincons IT team along with a number of "Prototyping Labs", one for each Use Case. Each prototyping lab lasted about one month. We thus proceed outlining the final documents (Deliverable) produced by Fincons, with the results of the research pipeline. These documents can be also found in the attachments to this Deliverable 4.4 (files A01_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo1-UCo6 - LatinAncientGreek V.1 March 2025; A02_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo1-UCo6 - LatinAncientGreek V.2 May 2025; A02_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo2 - UCo4 - Church Slavonic_Vector Similarity Search for Old Church Slavonic Texts;

Ao4_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo2 - Arabic_Building a Semantic Search System for Medieval Arabic TextsFincons; Ao5_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo9 - Latin August 2025).

The prototyping labs carried out with Fincons primarily enabled the development of the semantic analysis and retrieval tools for the individual languages addressed in WP4 (with the exception of Sanskrit, see below). These tools constitute core outcomes of the WP and were progressively integrated into DaMSym, the project platform dedicated to semantic retrieval in the selected languages. References to each tool are provided in the Technical Data Sheets, while the detailed technical specifications and development workflows are documented in the deliverables produced at the end of each prototyping lab. Both sets of documents have been shared with the reviewer. In this sense, the prototyping activities are not separate experiments, but rather structured development phases directly contributing to the core WP results.

Two exceptions require clarification: the cases of Latin and Greek, and the case of Sanskrit.

In the case of Latin, by contrast, the prototyping lab produced the Lamba model, which is openly available as an independent outcome; however, the encoder currently implemented in DaMSym for Latin is SPhilBERTa. This distinction reflects a technical choice made during benchmarking and integration: while the Latin prototyping lab successfully produced a SSM, this model proved to be still less performing compared to SPhilBERTa. Thus, SPhilBERTa was exploited to process the embedding of all corpuses. All tools produced during the Fincons prototyping labs, including those not directly deployed in DaMSym, are nevertheless referenced in the Technical Data Sheet and documented in the relevant attachments.

The Sanskrit case represents a further specific situation. The data reported in the Technical Data Sheet refer to the initial development phase carried out with the University of Palermo and not to a Fincons prototyping lab. The work conducted by Fincons on Sanskrit semantic retrieval belongs to a second development phase of the project, which began in mid-January 2026 and therefore falls outside the temporal scope of the present document. Unlike the other languages, this phase was not organized as a prototyping lab but was carried out autonomously by Fincons in collaboration with the ITSERR PMO. Its primary objective was to adapt and harmonize the Sanskrit tool with the general architectural and functional standards of the DaMSym platform, while preserving the linguistic and methodological specificities defined during the earlier development phase with the University of Palermo. The overall goal was to ensure coherence across the semantic retrieval platform while maintaining language-specific features where required. For this reason, the subsequent User Acceptance Testing (UAT) phase involved not only the Fincons technical team, but also the researcher responsible for the Sanskrit case study, the WP Product Owners, and the project PMO.

Latin and Ancient Greek

UC 01 - V.1 and V.2 - SimCSE Fintetuning of SPhilBERTa

This prototyping timebox took place over the course of February 2025, with the first version of the deliverable submitted on March 15. The goal of the prototyping was to apply unsupervised fine-tuning techniques—SimCSE—to the Sphilberta (Riemenscheider and Frank, 2023b) model, with the aim of obtaining a version adapted for semantic retrieval in Greek, Latin, and cross-lingual contexts. However, upon careful examination, it was observed that the models produced, at any checkpoint, were unable to perform any semantic discrimination. Internal clarifications with Fincons revealed certain misalignments during the training and evaluation phases, which were documented in a

second deliverable submitted by Fincons on May 15. Both the deliverable documents are included in the attachments (Ao1_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo1-UCo6 - LatinAncientGreek V.1 March 2025; Ao2_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo1-UCo6 - LatinAncientGreek V.2 May 2025).

UC o6 - Lamba, a Latin Mamba

This prototyping timebox took place over the course of August 2025. The set objective was to explore new technologies alternative to transformers for performing semantic retrieval in Latin. The outcome consisted of adapting a Mamba model to the Latin language, resulting in the Lamba model, soon to be publicly released. The deliverable document produced by Fincons was submitted to WP4 on September 2, 2025.

Church Slavonic

UCo4 - Adapting Vector Similarity Search for Old Church Slavonic Texts

This prototyping lab lasted for one month (late April to late May). To prepare the Old Church Slavonic textual data for semantic embedding and search, a chunking strategy aimed at segmenting long texts into semantically meaningful units has been adopted. The dataset used was provided in two separate JSON files: 1) DIACU, whose information can be found in the attached document , containing 652 entries (see Ao8_Technical Data Sheet); 2) other texts subject to partial copyright, provided as part of a collaboration with Professor Viktor Baranov (manuscript.ru), specifically including texts from the 11th century and transcriptions of manuscripts from the Kazanskaya Collection (32 texts in total).

Since the dataset comprises texts collected from various digital libraries, a major challenge in the development of the tool was the visualization. This issue was addressed by applying the specific font corresponding to the library from which each text was sourced. In the case of Cyrillomethodiana, to resolve backend visualization problems, a manually created mapping between Unicode and PUA codes was also applied. The deliverable of this prototyping lab, which can be found in the attachment (Ao2_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo2 - UCo4 - Church Slavonic_Vector Similarity Search for Old Church Slavonic Texts), was submitted on May 30, 2025.

The other tools produced within the scope of the Slavic case study were developed in collaboration with CNR-ISTI in Pisa and the University of Palermo. Further information can be found in the forms attached to this document (Ao8_Technical Data Sheet).

For the sake of completeness, and in light of the reviewer's remarks concerning the non-functioning links (which correspond to tool code intended for local installation, as the tools are not available on the marketplace), reference is made here to the following GitHub repository.

Converter: <https://github.com/usmannawazo1/OCS-Text-Processing>

Lemmatizer: <https://github.com/usmannawazo1/Old-Church-Slavonic-Lemmatizer>

Combined tool: <https://github.com/usmannawazo1/ocscombined>

Arabic

UCo2- Building a Semantic Search System for Medieval Arabic Texts

The present prototyping lab lasted slightly more than one month and was conducted between 12 March and 24 April 2025. The aim of the prototyping lab was to develop a comprehensive system enabling semantic search over texts drawn from the OpenITI corpus of medieval Arabic sources, with

a particular focus on works dating from the 12th to the 15th centuries CE (600–900 Anno Hegirae - AH), as well as on a selected subset of texts spanning a different chronological range. Specifically, the work was carried out on KITAB, the Arabic subcorpus of OpenITI, which comprises more than 30 GB of textual data along with extensive metadata. The corpus primarily contains premodern works ranging from the origins of Arabic literature up to approximately the 9th century AH. The task performed aimed to reorganize this material in a more rational structure and in a more reduced and manageable form, suitable for semantic processing.

The system is designed to provide scholars with a powerful tool for discovering relevant passages across multiple classical texts based on semantic similarity, rather than simple keyword matching. In order to enhance the functionality of a semantic retrieval tool applied to Arabic texts, it was necessary to intervene at the level of the tool's reference dataset and its associated metadata.

Further details concerning the pipeline adopted during the prototyping lab are provided in the attached deliverable (Ao4_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo2 - Deliverable_Building a Semantic Search System for Medieval Arabic Texts).

Sanskrit

As regards Sanskrit, two tools will be published on the ITSERR Marketplace as source code (the Sandhisplitter and the Sanskrit Word Search Engine) and as a tool incorporated together with the other languages of WP4, Sanskrit DaMSYM. We held several meetings with Fincons, working on user stories to outline the features of Sanskrit DaMSym, defining the search fields that can be used and the metadata to be shown to users.

As for the work carried out by the two members of the team involved in the study of the Sanskrit language, Igor Spanò (RTDa in Indian Philosophy and Religions) and Irfan Ali (IT member), for each tool, the work done, purposes, results, period, output, and other essential details are as follows.

Sandhi Splitter Tool (published as Sourcecode):

Sanskrit is a morphologically and phonetically complex language. A major challenge in its processing is splitting compound words that are phonetically merged. Identifying the correct split locations is difficult, as many possible splits exist, but only a few are semantically valid. Sandhi splitting is crucial for the accurate understanding and analysis of Sanskrit texts, as it clarifies the meaning of each word within compounds. We proposed an Attention-Based Bi-Encoder model to predict valid split locations in Sanskrit compound words. This model enhances text understanding, supports digital preservation, and aids in uncovering the cultural and historical significance of Sanskrit literature. It serves as a valuable tool for scholars, simplifying compound word analysis and improving the interpretation of Sanskrit texts. The proposed model correctly identifies where the compound word should be split into its components in 89.27% of cases, outperforming the state-of-the-art technique. We used an augmented dataset that incorporates the UoH dataset, featuring challenging compound words drawn from the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit repository.

Sanskrit- Word Search Engine (published as Sourcecode):

A specialized word search engine was developed for exploring Sanskrit corpora, including both Vedic and non-Vedic texts. This tool allows users to search for one to four words, featuring an advanced filtering system not found in existing tools. Additionally, the retrieved words are displayed along with their relative positions within the sentence, providing deeper insights. The tool was created to offer more precise textual searches for scholars, enabling them to focus on specific materials relevant to their research in philology, history, and religious texts. The advanced filter allows users to target Vedic ritual texts or non-Vedic and later-period sources. The tool provides accurate and relevant search results, greatly enhancing research capabilities. It aids in narrowing down materials pertinent to the user's specific research goals. A user manual was also prepared to guide researchers on effectively utilizing the tool. The development and implementation of the tool occurred over the course of the Vedic and non-Vedic eras. The output of this project is a highly functional word search engine, a user manual, and an enhanced research tool that significantly aids scholars in Indology.

Sanskrit DaMSym:

We have developed a Sanskrit semantic retrieval system that enables users to search and retrieve semantically similar sentences from a large corpus of Sanskrit texts. The goal of this work is to move

beyond keyword-based search and build a linguistically and contextually aware retrieval system for Sanskrit literature. To achieve this, we utilize the IndicBERTv2-MLM-only model, a transformer-based encoder with 12 layers and 768-dimensional hidden representations, to generate deep contextual embeddings of Sanskrit sentences. In our pipeline, the model's first and last layer outputs are averaged to obtain rich token representations, which are then combined using an IDF-weighted pooling technique that emphasizes semantically important words. The resulting sentence embeddings are z-score normalized to ensure a consistent vector space. These embeddings are then indexed using FAISS (Facebook AI Similarity Search), an efficient library for high-speed vector similarity search based on L2-normalized embeddings, allowing us to perform semantic retrieval through cosine similarity. For user interaction, we developed an intuitive Gradio-based graphical interface (GUI) that allows two modes of querying: (1) sentence-level search, where the system retrieves the most semantically similar sentences, and (2) focus-word-based search, where results are ranked by the similarity of a specific word's meaning in context. The complete system thus integrates transformer-based embeddings, statistical weighting (IDF), and efficient vector indexing (FAISS) to enable context-aware retrieval of Sanskrit texts. This framework lays the foundation for advanced research in semantic search for low-resource, morphologically rich languages such as Sanskrit. We used data from the Digital Corpus of Sanskrit (DCS) repository for this semantic retrieval.

Performance and Impact

This section, Performance and Impact, provides an assessment of the outcomes of these activities, highlighting the effectiveness, limitations, and potential contributions of the work activities of WP4. The section is structured around two main documents that are reported in the attachments: Key Performance Indicators (KPI) at bimonthly 15 (March-April 2025 - intermediate reference before the final indicators document referred at bimonthly 21 March-April 2026) and the Impact Document.

The two documents show that WP4-DaMSym has achieved overall strong scientific, technological, and social results, with high performance in sentence retrieval tools for the main languages (around or above 80%), very positive academic feedback (80% positive, 0% negative), and a significant impact on research, training, and cultural valorization. However, some critical issues remain, including delays in certain milestones, cross-lingual development still to be fully assessed, and notably weaker performance in Church Slavonic (lemmatization and combined pipeline), as well as structural limits related to data/OCR quality, interdisciplinary coordination, and human resources. From a managerial and infrastructural perspective, structured risk mitigation measures have been implemented (delays, security, data loss, partner conflicts) with periodic monitoring systems. Strategically, further optimization of Church Slavonic tools, improved data collection on policy impact, and consolidation of KPI dashboards and validation processes are recommended to enhance scalability and long-term impact of WP4.

See documents Ao6_Impact WP4 and Ao7_KPI WP4 BM 15 in the attachments.

Compared to the document previously submitted to the reviewer, these data have partially changed, with specific reference to the impact of the lemmatization tool and the combined lemmatization–conversion tool for Old Church Slavonic. This change is attributable to the inclusion of a linguistic reviewer in the team, made possible through dedicated contracts activated from mid-2025 onward, as well as to the adoption of the Stanza model for training the lemmatizer (following suggestions that emerged from the evaluation forms completed by experts for Deliverable 4.1.2).

See documents:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JaFX5Kkv1VJoDzYp9FPfalsqnl-8ZZSx/edit>

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1h3PgTaGZsEjlbKiy15qDVKCCFaPWfGjy/edit>

The updated data will be presented in the final document concerning impact assessment and KPIs.

Attachments

- 1) Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab, Use Cases from WP4- Deliverables
 - A01_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo1-UCo6 - LatinAncientGreek V.1 March 2025
 - A02_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo1-UCo6 - LatinAncientGreek V.2 May 2025
 - A02_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo2 - UCo4 - Church Slavonic_Vector Similarity Search for Old Church Slavonic Texts
 - A04_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo2 - Arabic_Building a Semantic Search System for Medieval Arabic Texts
 - A05_Fincons - ITSERR Prototyping Lab UCo9 - Latin August 2025
- 2) Impact and Management
 - A06_Impact WP4
 - A07_KPI WP4 BM 15
- 3) Materials produced by WP4
 - A08_Technical Data Sheet
 - A09_Screenshots